

1 **Supplemental Information**

2 **Colloidal physics modeling reveals how per-ribosome productivity increases with growth**
3 **rate in *E. coli***

4

5 Appendix SA. Colloidal Smoldyn theoretical framework and simulation implementation

6 Here, we briefly describe the theoretical framework that underlies Colloidal Smoldyn and provide
7 simulation implementation details for transport and reaction dynamics.

8 *9 Simulating colloidal transport dynamics*

10 The transport dynamics of water-suspended particles of size ~ 1.5 nm to O(10) microns (colloids)
11 have been thoroughly studied and characterized in the microhydrodynamics and colloid physics
12 literature. Fluid motion generated by particle motion at these length scales is governed by the
13 Stokes equations, while particle motion is described by the N-particle Langevin equation (1),

$$14 \quad \mathbf{m} \cdot \frac{d\mathbf{U}}{dt} = \mathbf{F}^B + \mathbf{F}^P + \mathbf{F}^{ext} + \mathbf{F}^H, \quad (1)$$

15 a stochastic force balance, where particle momentum $\mathbf{m} \cdot d\mathbf{U}/dt$ equates the sum of the forces \mathbf{F}
16 that act on the particles. Here \mathbf{m} is a diagonal tensor containing the details of the mass of the
17 particles and \mathbf{U} is the particles' velocity vector. The forces \mathbf{F} represent the stochastic forces \mathbf{F}^B
18 that give rise to Brownian motion, the deterministic interparticle forces \mathbf{F}^P that here arise from a
19 hard-sphere potential, the external forces \mathbf{F}^{ext} that could represent either active motion or
20 externally induced motion, and hydrodynamic drag forces \mathbf{F}^H that arise due to the difference
21 between the particle velocity \mathbf{U} and imposed fluid motion \mathbf{u}^∞ . Each of the vectors (\mathbf{U} and \mathbf{F}) has
22 dimensions 3N describing the three-dimensional space in which all N particles move. In our system
23 there are no external forces on the particles, thus $\mathbf{F}^{ext} = 0$.

24 The Brownian force \mathbf{F}_i^B on a given particle "i" arises from collisions between the colloidal particle
25 and the solvent molecules as the fluid fluctuates thermally and follows Gaussian statistics,

$$26 \quad \overline{\mathbf{F}_i^B} = \mathbf{0} \\ \overline{\mathbf{F}_i^B(0)\mathbf{F}_i^B(t)} = 2kT(6\pi\eta a_i)\mathbf{I}\delta(t), \quad (2)$$

27 where k is the Boltzmann constant, T is the absolute temperature, η is the solvent viscosity, a_i is
28 the particle radius, \mathbf{I} is the identity tensor, and $\delta(t)$ is the Dirac delta function. The overbar
29 considers averages over times long compared to the solvent molecule timescale, such that a
30 colloidal particle has undergone many random and decorrelated impacts from solvent molecules.
31 Although the mean Brownian force is zero, its covariance, $2kT(6\pi\eta a_i)\mathbf{I}$, has an amplitude set by
32 the fluctuation-dissipation theorem, which dictates that colloidal motion due to thermal forces is
33 dissipated viscously back into the solvent. In our system, we approximated the drag force on the
34 colloid, $(6\pi\eta a_i)\mathbf{I}$, to be constant, where each particle experiences solvent drag and excludes other
35 particles entropically with finite size, but coupled hydrodynamic interactions are neglected. This
36 common simplification, the "freely draining model" is appropriate for gaining understanding of
37 the basic colloidal physics of a suspension (2–6) and is accurate in many physiological conditions.
38 Incorporating hydrodynamic interactions in such models is routine (7–10) although
39 computationally expensive and will be discussed in future work.

40 Interactions between colloidal particles can be attractive or repulsive and range from short- to long
41 interparticle distances. In the present work, biomolecules are represented as hard spheres: they
42 interact only at contact at which point we stipulate that they may not overlap. This can be
43 represented mathematically via a hard-sphere potential that enforces an infinite penalty for overlap.
44 The gradient of this entropic exclusion gives rise to a deterministic interparticle force between two
45 particles of radius a_i and a_j

46
$$\mathbf{F}_i^P = \frac{a_j}{a_j + a_i} kT \delta[r_{ij} - (a_j + a_i)] \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{ij}, \quad (3)$$

47 where r_{ij} is the interparticle distance between the particles' centers, $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{ij}$ is the unit vector along the
 48 line that connects the particle centers, and the delta function δ enforces the infinite penalty for
 49 overlap.

50 Finally, the hydrodynamic drag forces are given by the Stokes drag on each particle according to

51
$$\mathbf{F}_i^H = 6\pi\eta a_i (\mathbf{U}_i - \mathbf{u}^\infty). \quad (4)$$

52 Overall, the fluid motion is governed by Stokes' equations; hence, particle dynamics operate in
 53 the "overdamped limit" of the Langevin equation, where integrating twice over a time interval Δt
 54 large enough for a colloid to have received many uncorrelated solvent molecule impacts and to
 55 have relaxed their momenta ($\Delta t \gg m/6\pi\eta a_i$) results in the displacement equation (see Ermak and
 56 McCammon, 1977 for further details)

57
$$\Delta \mathbf{x}_i = \mathbf{X}_i(\Delta t) + \frac{\mathbf{F}_i^P}{6\pi\eta a_i} \Delta t + \mathbf{u}^\infty \Delta t. \quad (5)$$

58 Here, $\Delta \mathbf{x}_i$ is the change in position over a time step Δt , owing to the combined contributions of
 59 the Brownian force, the interparticle potential, and the imposed flow. In **Equation 5**, the Brownian
 60 displacement $\mathbf{X}_i(\Delta t)$ obeys Gaussian statistics given by

61
$$\overline{\mathbf{X}_i} = \mathbf{0}$$

$$\overline{\mathbf{X}_i(\Delta t) \mathbf{X}_i(\Delta t)} = 2\mathbf{D}_i \Delta t, \quad (6)$$

62 where the amplitude of the co-variance in this freely draining model is set by the diffusion
 63 coefficient of a single particle defined by the familiar Stokes-Einstein relation, $\mathbf{D}_i =$
 64 $kT/6\pi\eta a_i \mathbf{I}$ (12, 13). In other approaches, the diffusion coefficient used to compute Brownian
 65 displacements is sometimes obtained from *in vivo* measurements in order to implicitly encode the
 66 effects of crowding but limits the applicability of the model to a specific temperature or crowding
 67 condition of the cell (among other issues). In our approach, the effects of crowding on particle
 68 motion emerge naturally from the excluded volume interactions enforced by the interparticle force
 69 (**Equation 3**): each particle undergoes a Brownian displacement commensurate with **Equation 6**,
 70 reflecting the dissipation of a thermal kick via its own solvent drag. However, over many
 71 displacements, a particle will encounter other particles and must "wait" for them to move in order
 72 to sample that space, leading naturally to a slow-down of diffusion over longer distances through
 73 a crowded suspension. Changes in volume fraction thus seamlessly lead to changes in particle
 74 dynamics and interactions.

75 The hard-sphere interparticle force (**Equation 3**) imposes a singular force between particles at
 76 contact. The modeling of singular forces in dynamic simulation is intractable; at best, very steep
 77 repulsions can be captured. To overcome this limitation, rather than to impose a singularity, we
 78 utilized a "potential-free" algorithm (14, 15), where once Brownian and imposed flow
 79 displacements are made, particles are permitted tiny overlaps which are then corrected. A pair of
 80 particles do not interact at all unless they come into direct contact or overlap and once they do
 81 interact, the hard-sphere displacement of each corrects any overlap:
 82

83
$$\Delta \mathbf{x}_i^{HS} = \frac{a_j}{a_j + a_i} [\Delta r_{ij} - (a_j + a_i)] H(a_j + a_i - \Delta r_{ij}) \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{ij}. \quad (7)$$

84 Here, $\Delta r_{ij} - (a_j + a_i)$ is the overlap being corrected, the Heaviside step function H ensures that
 85 particles are displaced only when they overlap, and $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{ij}$ is the unit vector along the line that connects
 86 the particle centers, giving the hard-sphere displacement along the line of centers. This approach
 87 is equivalent to applying to each particle an interparticle force \mathbf{F}_i^P that is proportional to the overlap
 88 to ensure entropic exclusion. The physical consequence of the hard-sphere interaction and the
 89 overlap correction is a contribution to the osmotic pressure that arises from the finite volume
 90 particles occupy in the suspension (16).

91 Incorporating in **Equation 5** the potential-free algorithm and considering that in our system there
 92 are no imposed flows \mathbf{u}^∞ gives a displacement equation of the form

93
$$\Delta \mathbf{x}_i = \Delta \mathbf{x}_i^{HS} + \mathbf{X}_i(\Delta t), \quad (8)$$

94 where $\Delta \mathbf{x}_i^{HS}$ is the displacement that enforces the hard-sphere potential. **Equations 6 – 8** constitute
 95 the framework underlying dynamic simulations in Colloidal Smoldyn, our adaptation of the
 96 original Smoldyn.

97 In our simulations, we chose a timestep $\Delta t = 62$ picoseconds empirically by testing the temporal
 98 resolution necessary to recover expected mean-squared displacements over long timescales, which
 99 we computed using the open-source LAMMPS Molecular Dynamics Simulator, across the levels
 100 of crowding we modeled (**Figure S3**) (17). Practically, this timestep corresponds to an average
 101 Brownian displacement per-timestep of 0.1 nm for ribosomes, 0.14 nm for ternary complexes, and
 102 0.25 nm for proteins (**Equation 6, Table S4**).

103 At each time step all particles have a Brownian displacement, after which the algorithm checks for
 104 overlaps between particles. In Colloidal Smoldyn, overlapping biomolecules are separated along
 105 their line of centers and placed at contact according to $\Delta \mathbf{x}^{HS}$ (**Equation 7**) and in accordance with
 106 well-established and experimentally validated models of colloidal physics (14). Our
 107 implementation is a direct modification to the physics represented by the original Smoldyn
 108 algorithm; the prior method over-corrects the overlap by separating the pair’s surfaces by the full
 109 distance, meaning a gap is introduced almost as though the collision was being modeled as inertial
 110 (18). In addition, the particles were moved not along their line of centers in the original algorithm
 111 but rather at a reflected angle again reminiscent of an inertial collision which is not appropriate for
 112 colloids in the overdamped dynamics limit. The original method of Smoldyn, although intuitive,
 113 is physically incorrect for systems in which fluid motion is governed by Stokes equations, and a
 114 strong drag force is exerted on the approaching molecules. In such systems inertia is irrelevant,
 115 meaning that when two particles approach after receiving a Brownian kick they will simply slow
 116 down until another Brownian displacement sets them in a different direction. Placing particles at
 117 contact along the line of centers upon overlap approximates this entropic exclusion interaction and
 118 the interparticle forces associated with this displacement contributes to the osmotic pressure of the
 119 suspension. The Heyes and Melrose algorithm has been shown to recover suspension osmotic
 120 pressure as predicted by statistical mechanics models (15, 19).

121 In simulations of crowded systems, correcting a set of overlaps typically produces additional new
 122 overlaps, necessitating additional iterations of overlap correction. Two strategies are applied to
 123 accurately process overlaps: first, utilizing short, discretized time steps to generate smaller and
 124 fewer overlaps; second, executing several overlap-correction cycles. For computational efficiency,

125 the original Smoldyn algorithm executed only one round of overlaps, leaving many still-
126 overlapping particles. Only in dilute systems is such an approximation physically accurate. In
127 colloidal Smoldyn, we conducted an optimization study to identify an appropriate balance of
128 efficiency and accuracy, from which we devised an algorithm with three iterations of overlap
129 resolution at the chosen timestep of $\Delta t = 62$ picoseconds.

130 In all our simulations, we avoided finite-size and boundary effects by implementing periodic
131 boundary conditions. The voxel sizes are large enough to avoid finite-size effects; we show that
132 voxels produce accurate physical structure and dynamics, by showing that the pair-correlation
133 function for all pairs decays well within the voxel (**Figure S15**). As further evidence, the long-
134 time self-diffusivity measured in LAMMPS was done with a system 100 times larger (in volume);
135 agreement with our results in Smoldyn is excellent (**Figure S3**).

136 *Simulating reaction dynamics*

137 In our simulations, after a ternary complex and unbound ribosome interact both biomolecules are
138 converted to form a single bound-ribosome that either disassociates or forms a peptide bond
139 following single-molecule rate kinetics. A bound ribosome has the same radius as an unbound
140 ribosome (an approximation of bound ribosomes internalizing tRNA during codon recognition).
141 In the native Smoldyn algorithm, the distance at which chemical interactions are initiated between
142 molecules is set *a priori* to be different than contact (e.g., molecules may be set to only react when
143 halfway overlapping or conversely while still separated by several molecule diameters). In
144 particular, the initiating distance is computed such that the overall reaction rate of all molecules in
145 simulation is equal to experimentally-measured kinetic rates set for individual reactions (20). This
146 approximation is based on the Smoluchowski model for reactions and is only reasonable for dilute
147 systems (or systems of point particles). To achieve a more physical representation for crowded
148 colloidal systems (as in our modeling of transport) that allows ab initio estimates of latency without
149 fitting, we further modified the Smoldyn algorithm in Colloidal Smoldyn to only allow for
150 initiation of chemical reactions upon the physical (entropic) interaction of reactant biomolecules.
151 We did not consider factors such as binding site orientation that would restrict reactions to only
152 certain interactions or reaction activation energies that may need to be overcome prior to reaction.
153 Instead, we made the approximation that all physical interactions between ternary complexes and
154 ribosomes (i.e., overlaps between ternary complexes and unbound ribosomes at the end of a
155 diffusive step) lead to reactions. Ribosomes and ternary complexes that disassociate following a
156 reaction are placed at contact, congruent to the Brownian dynamics underlying our modeling of
157 transport. This was a final modification to the Smoldyn algorithm, which places biomolecules at a
158 distance following disassociation to artificially reduce repeat reaction probability based on fitting
159 of experimental single molecule reaction kinetic parameters (an approximation that, as before, is
160 reasonable only for dilute systems) (20).

161 We computed the time a ternary complex spends bound to a ribosome via a Markov process
162 consisting of well-defined intra-ribosomal states and transition kinetic rates (k_i) (21). Specifically,
163 the algorithm we used to model biochemical reactions involving ternary complex-bound ribosomes
164 is:

- 165 1. For each state transition $i \rightarrow j$ out of the current state i , draw a transition dwell time,
166 $\tau_{i \rightarrow j} \leftarrow \exp\left(\frac{1}{k_{i \rightarrow j}}\right)$;
- 167 2. Transition to state j corresponding to the fastest transition time, $\operatorname{argmin}_j(\tau_{i \rightarrow j})$;

- 168 3. Draw an updated dwell time for the transition to state j , $\tau_{i \rightarrow j} \leftarrow \exp\left(\operatorname{argmin}_j(\tau_{i \rightarrow j})\right)$;
- 169 4. Add the updated dwell time, $\tau_{i \rightarrow j}$, to total dwell time τ_{tot} ;
- 170 5. Repeat until either the ternary complex dissociates from the ribosome or a peptide bond
- 171 is successfully formed.

172 Using our algorithm and reported kinetic rates, we computed the distributions of latencies for non-
173 cognate, near-cognate, and cognate ternary complexes reacting with ribosomes (**Figure S2, Table**
174 **S5, ReactionKineticsCalculations.ipynb**). We did not consider the unlikely events of incorrect
175 reactions leading to mis-incorporated amino acids ($\leq 1\%$) or cognate ternary complexes being
176 rejected following successful codon recognition (0.04%). The overall processing order of our
177 algorithm is: first diffusive transport of molecules, then reactions between overlapping molecules,
178 and then overlap resolution.

179

180 **Note S1. Sensitivity analysis and the impact of parameter values**

181 We sought to understand if our prediction that the productivity of individual ribosomes increases
182 due to stoichiometric crowding is sensitive to the fact that our unfitted model does not exactly
183 match observations of absolute elongation latencies. One natural place to start is to make a change
184 in the values of the chemical kinetic parameters used in our model, which are taken from *in vitro*
185 measurements (**Table S5**). The rationale for modulating these parameters is that *in vitro* kinetic
186 rates may differ from their *in vivo* values due to, for example, differences in salt concentrations *in*
187 *vitro* compared to *in vivo* (**Figure S13A**). To test this idea, we implemented a uniform three-fold
188 increase of all intra-ribosomal chemical kinetic rates in our model. We then simulated ensembles
189 of translation voxels at varying growth rates and measured the resulting elongation rates. This
190 chemical-parameter change closed the quantitative gap: elongation latency ($\bar{\tau}_{\text{elong}} =$
191 100 ms at 0.6 dbl/hr to 45 ms at 3.0 dbl/hr) now matched experimental latency ($\tau_{\text{elong}}^{\text{bulk}} =$
192 83 ms at 0.6 dbl/hr to 48 ms at 3.0 dbl/hr) (**Figure S13B**). Importantly, the speedup in elongation
193 as growth quickens occurs even with the higher chemical kinetic rates used to fit the bulk
194 experimental observations.

195 We also sought to test if our predicted increase in ribosome productivity requires physical
196 transport. To do so we stress-tested the sensitivity of elongation to changes in transport by
197 modeling instantaneous transport within our voxel ensembles (**Methods**). We found that the
198 growth-rate dependence of elongation latency is lost when transport is modeled as an instantaneous
199 process (**triangles in Figure S13B, Figures S6, S7**), demonstrating the essential role of transport
200 physics in the growth-rate dependence of elongation rate, and also demonstrating the criticality of
201 accurate chemical parameters in establishing absolute quantitative prediction of elongation
202 latency.

203 **Note S2. Translation initiation latency relative to translation elongation latency**

204 Translation initiation is slow compared to a single elongation step. Therefrom, one
205 might naively expect initiation to be rate limiting to protein synthesis overall and, thus, expect that
206 any increase in protein synthesis rates should mostly arise due to increases in the rate of initiation.

207 However, clues to the contrary are apparent. For example, there is overwhelming experimental
208 evidence from work to optimize expression of heterologous proteins (22). Specifically,
209 synonymous changes in coding sequences that require ribosomes to make the same protein via
210 coding-sequence unique elongation processes produce dramatic changes in protein synthesis rates
211 and abundances. That is, codon usage changes alone can result in changes in gene expression

212 levels, ranging from undetectable to majority of cell protein. This strong impact on protein
213 synthesis rate is solely due to impacts on translation elongation, not translation initiation. Studies
214 of natural living systems further reveal a literature that advances how both translation initiation
215 and elongation can limit protein synthesis rates, depending on conditions (23, 24).

216 Nevertheless, it is important to consider initiation more formally and explain why elongation is
217 most likely to underlie increases in overall protein synthesis rates. To this end, we return to the
218 conventional view of translation elongation in which the correct ternary
219 complex instantaneously presents itself to the ribosome exactly when needed (i.e., they appear
220 instantaneously in exactly the right order). That is, a situation in which there is no additional
221 latency due to physical transport, nor combinatorial sampling by and among competing ternary
222 complexes (i.e., setting aside the fact that our work shows that most elongation latency arises from
223 transport, not kinetics). In these unrealizable conditions, the rate of peptide bond formation is
224 entirely determined by chemical kinetics and is about 42 ms per amino acid. By comparison,
225 translation initiation should be much slower, taking about 1-12 seconds. But protein synthesis
226 requires not just one elongation step but hundreds in series (i.e., the average protein in *E. coli* is
227 ~333 amino acids). Considering elongation of the entire protein, we estimate ~14 seconds total
228 just from chemical kinetic latency alone (42 ms per amino acid). Thus, it becomes apparent that,
229 while the chemical kinetics of a single initiation event might be relatively slow, most of the time
230 is spent in the elongation phase (e.g., 12 seconds for initiation vs. at least 14 seconds for
231 elongation).

232 **Note S3. Estimating the evolutionary impact of increasing ribosome productivity**

233 To explore the potential evolutionary impact of increasing ribosome productivity, we estimated
234 how much slower bacterial growth would be if ribosome productivity did not increase (i.e.,
235 remained fixed) and only the abundances of translation machinery increased.

236 For a cell to replicate, it must replicate all its protein machinery. Since a fraction of peptide bonds
237 formed during cell replication belong to translation machinery, as individual cells grow, increased
238 translation machinery should enable more total peptide bonds to be formed per unit time. We can
239 estimate the lower and upper bounds of total peptide bond formation in the time cells typically
240 take to double, and thus growth rate, by assuming that this fraction is 0 (i.e., a lower bound in
241 which no new peptide bonds enable more translation) and by assuming this fraction is 1 (i.e., an
242 upper bound in which all new peptide bonds are incorporated into ribosomes that enable more
243 translation).

244 As a lower bound estimate,

$$245 \quad \text{Lower bound total bond formation} = N_{\text{rib}} * t_{\text{dbl}} * k. \quad (\text{S1})$$

246 As an upper bound estimate,

$$247 \quad \text{Upper bound total bond formation} = \text{aa}_{\text{rib}} * N_{\text{rib}} * \left[\exp \left(t_{\text{dbl}} * \frac{k}{\text{aa}_{\text{rib}}} \right) - 1 \right]. \quad (\text{S2})$$

248 Here, $t_{\text{dbl}} = \mu/3600$ is the time in seconds per cell doubling and $\text{aa}_{\text{rib}} = 7336$ amino
249 acids/ribosome is the number of amino acids in a ribosome.

250 At $\mu = 3.0$, there are on average $N_{\text{rib}} = 62000$ actively elongating ribosomes per cell elongating
251 at a rate of $k = 21$ amino acids/s, leading to:

252 Lower bound total bond formation = 1,562,400,000 bonds, and

253 Upper bound total bond formation = 13,660,863,648 bonds.

254 As a sanity check, we can estimate the total bonds in a cell at $\mu = 3.0$ dbl/hr from the total bonds
255 composing proteins and total (active and non-active) ribosomes (**Table S1, S4**): 7.78×10^6
256 proteins * 264 aa/average-sized protein + 73000 total ribosomes * $aa_{rib} = 2,589,448,000$ bonds,
257 which lies between the lower and upper bounds as expected.

258 We can next consider the hypothetical case in which ribosome productivity at $\mu = 3.0$ dbl/hr does
259 not increase and instead remains fixed at that of $\mu = 0.6$ dbl/hr, $k' = 12$ amino acids/s. In this
260 case, we can estimate the lower bound and upper bound time needed for total bond formation by
261 solving for t_{dbl} in equations S1 and S2.

262 In the lower bound case,

$$263 \quad \text{Lower bound } t'_{dbl} = \frac{N_{rib} * k'}{\text{Lower bound total bond formation}}. \quad (S3)$$

264 In the upper bound case,

$$265 \quad \text{Upper bound } t_{dbl}' = \frac{aa_{rib}}{k'} * \ln \left(\frac{\text{Upper bound total bond formation}}{aa_{rib} * N_{rib}} + 1 \right). \quad (S4)$$

266 This gives us,

267 Lower bound $t_{dbl}' = 2100$ s, giving an effective $\mu' = 1.7$ dbl/hr

268 Upper bound $t_{dbl}' = 2100$ s, giving an effective $\mu' = 1.7$ dbl/hr

269 Thus, we estimate that maximum observed cell doubling would proceed at ~ 1.7 dbl/hr instead of
270 3.0 dbl/hr in the hypothetical case in which ribosome productivity did not increase and remained
271 fixed at that of $\mu = 0.6$ dbl/hr.

272 What would this difference mean practically from an evolutionary perspective? We can compare
273 the expected growth of microbes with these different growth rates:

$$274 \quad \text{Fold-difference microbes} = 2^{(\mu - \mu')t}. \quad (S5)$$

275 After $t = 6$ hours there would be ~ 200 -fold more of the microbes with increased ribosome
276 productivity, after 12 hours $\sim 50,000$ -fold more, and after 24 hours 2.5 billion-fold more.

277 **Note S4. On the relation of our modeling to other modeling methods**

278 *Mass-action kinetic models.* Mass-action kinetics models of translation elongation such as that by
279 Klumpp et al. abstract away space and stochasticity entirely, approximating diffusion by inserting
280 a value for a diffusion coefficient into a mass balance. In contrast we explicitly represent space,
281 modeling Brownian motion in our simulations directly from the Langevin equation and intra-
282 ribosomal reactions using a stochastic process (see **Appendix SA**).

283 Explicit consideration of spatial effects leads to significantly different system dynamics and thus
284 conclusions. One conclusion of the Klumpp et al. model, for example, is that when diffusion is
285 slower, reactions are slower and thus protein synthesis is slower. Yet, by considering spatial
286 implications of well-established experimental data here (25, 26), we find that *E. coli* becomes more
287 crowded as it grows faster; by then examining detailed particle trajectories, which captures varied
288 diffusion and transport times due to crowding, polydispersity, and spatial proximity, we find that
289 closer proximity between translation molecules boosts protein synthesis rates even when diffusion
290 slows down. Homogenized diffusion coefficients used in mass-action kinetics models, even

291 adjusted for growth rate and crowding, smear out underlying particle displacements, and thus come
292 to incorrect mechanistic conclusions in this case.

293 *Gillespie simulations.* A Gillespie simulation is a classic example of how to abstract away the
294 impact of molecular transport, searching, and encounters on the rate of reaction while maintaining
295 an approximation of stochasticity. A Gillespie model imports mass-action kinetics for reaction
296 rates and then uses this information to create a distribution of events over time. In our model, we
297 obtain a distribution of the time it takes for cognate or non-cognate ternary complexes to react with
298 ribosomes once bound. But the rate at which such reactions start (and thus complete) depends on
299 the probability of the cognate ternary complex encountering the ribosome. This is a statistically
300 independent (Brownian) physical search process that is explicitly represented in our simulations,
301 but which in the Gillespie algorithm would proceed instantly without any spatial consideration.
302 After many reactions using many voxels, our simulations will produce data that will recover the
303 smeared-out Gillespie simulation parameters; but our physical resolution reveals the mechanistic
304 process by which the Gillespie parameters speed up.

305 **Note S5. On the difference between mass density and volume fraction in cytoplasm**

306 The mass density and volume fraction of cytoplasm are independent quantities. A simple
307 illustration of this fact is that a kilo of lead (5cm x 5cm x 5cm) can easily fit inside a bag that
308 would be too small for a kilo of cork (23cm x 23cm x 23cm). A similar effect is at play in *E. coli*
309 cytoplasm as the cell adjusts its molecular composition across changes in growth rate. Volume
310 fraction changes independent of changes in mass density of cytoplasm (**Figure S17**) because the
311 mass density varies among individual biomolecules (e.g., proteins are five times denser than
312 ternary complexes). Thus, as the relative molecular abundances change, the occupied volume
313 fraction changes even if the overall mass density of the cell remains fixed (as illustrated in a
314 simplified case in **Figure S18**). In turn, since occupied volume determines the diffusivity in
315 cytoplasm, it is volume fraction rather than mass density that sets the diffusion coefficient involved
316 in cellular processes.

317

318 **Figure S1. Cell and translation voxel parameters vary with growth rate.** (A) Polynomial fits
 319 of reported cell parameter measurements (data points are taken from Tables S1, S2, and S3). (B)
 320 Estimate of protein abundances in cells across growth rates. (C) Estimate of ribosome, ternary
 321 complex, and protein abundances in translation voxels across growth rates. (D) Estimate of the
 322 polydispersity of translation voxels across growth rates.

323

324 **Figure S2. Ribosomal kinetics are dependent on whether a ternary complex is cognate, near-**
 325 **cognate, or non-cognate. (A-D):** Distribution of time spent by tRNA within ribosomes, computed
 326 by sampling tRNA-ribosome reaction trajectories. **(A)** Cognate ternary complexes that
 327 successfully react (probability shown). **(B)** Cognate ternary complexes that are rejected
 328 (probability shown). **(C)** Near-cognate ternary complexes that are rejected (only rejections are
 329 considered). **(D)** Non-cognate ternary complexes that are rejected (only rejections are
 330 considered). In each plot, average latency is marked by a blue line and displayed on the top right.

331

332 **Figure S3. The long-time self-diffusivity of ternary complexes is dependent on crowding and**
 333 **growth rate.** (A) Measurements of ternary complex mean squared displacement in translation
 334 voxels without proteins using Smoldyn. (B) Measurements of ternary complex mean squared
 335 displacement in complete translation voxels (i.e., with proteins) using Smoldyn. (C) Measurements
 336 of ternary complex mean squared displacement in complete translation voxels using LAMMPS.
 337 System size tested in LAMMPS is 100 times larger (in volume) than in Smoldyn to obtain better
 338 statistics and test finite size effects. Agreement with (B) and (C) and confirms the accuracy of our
 339 implementation in Smoldyn and that our voxels avoid finite size effects. For all plots, in the dilute
 340 limit, ternary complex long-time diffusivity should equal its short-time diffusivity ($D = 56 \mu\text{m}^2/s$,
 341 Table S4).

342

343 **Figure S4. The number of cognate and near-cognate ternary complexes in a translation voxel**
 344 **follows a slightly growth-rate dependent probability distribution. (A)** Distribution of cognate
 345 ternary complexes in translation voxels. **(B)** Distribution of near-cognate ternary complexes in
 346 translation voxels. Insets highlight the distribution between values of zero to ten cognate ternary
 347 complexes.

348

349
 350 **Figure S5. Predictions of translation latencies are insensitive to low and intermediate kinetic**
 351 **rate scaling due to differences in unbinding and mixing timescales. (A-C)** Elongation latency,
 352 transport latency, and reaction latency are insensitive to kinetic rate scaling at a scaling of less than
 353 ~ 2000 . Data shown for a translation voxel with growth rate $\mu = 3.0$ dbl/hr. **(D)** The average time
 354 ternary complexes take to unbind from ribosomes (unbinding time) remains slower than the typical
 355 time ternary complexes take to diffuse their radius within a voxel (mix time, as calculated in the
 356 Methods). The mix time plotted is computed for the most crowded growth condition ($\phi_{\text{vox}} = 0.42$,
 357 $\mu = 3.0$ dbl/hr).

358

359 **Figure S6. Repeat reactions between mismatching ternary complexes and ribosomes are**
 360 **sensitive to crowding and instantaneous transport.** Average number of repeat reactions
 361 following initial reaction in complete translation voxels (black curve, filled circles), translation
 362 voxels with no proteins (blue curve, x's), and translation voxels with instantaneous transport (red
 363 curve, triangles). Inset shows that simulations with instantaneous transport produce repeat
 364 reactions with uniform random likelihood across all growth rates.

365

366 **Figure S7. Growth rate dependence of transport and reaction latency is lost when transport**
 367 **is modeled as an instantaneous process.** Simulations with instantaneous transport (red curve,
 368 triangles) produce **(A)** transport latencies and **(B)** reaction latencies that are uniform across growth
 369 rates. Original simulation results are shown for comparison (black curve).

370

371 **Figure S8. The frequency of a given codon and their corresponding tRNA are weakly**
372 **correlated.** Frequency data from Table S6.

373

374 **Figure S9. Our chemical kinetics sensitivity analysis shows that only changes in unbinding**
 375 **rate (k_{1r}) or all kinetic rates together can speed up elongation to experimentally predicted**
 376 **latencies.** Each plot shows the elongation latencies (solid blue line) that result from scaling one or
 377 more intra-ribosomal kinetic rates (specified in top right) to be faster or slower compared to
 378 baseline (dashed blue line). All simulations were for translation voxels at $\mu = 3.0$ dbl/hr.
 379 Experimentally measured elongation latency at $\mu = 3.0$ dbl/hr is shown for reference (green line).
 380 Scales are identical across plots except for the k_{1r} and All rates plots.

381

382 **Figure S10. (A-C) Our simulation timestep sensitivity analysis shows that elongation latency,**
 383 **transport latency, and reaction latency each converge near our chosen timestep at the most**
 384 **crowded growth rate ($\mu = 3.0$ dbl/hr).** Experimentally measured elongation latency at $\mu = 3.0$
 385 dbl/hr is shown for reference in panel A (green line). **(D)** Numerical accuracy, computed as the
 386 percentage of entropic interactions between particles that are resolved, converges to 100% near
 387 our chosen timestep. All simulations were for translation voxels at $\mu = 3.0$ dbl/hr. The dashed line
 388 corresponds to the timestep used for simulations throughout the paper ($\Delta t = 62$ picoseconds).

389

390 **Figure S11. Cell and translation voxel parameters can be projected to faster-than-observed**
 391 **growth rates.** (A) Extrapolated cell parameter fits (bolded dashed lines) projecting beyond
 392 observed growth rates (solid lines) for ribosomes (circle values from Table S1), ternary complexes
 393 (circle values from Table S1), cell mass (circle values from Table S1), cell volume (circle values
 394 from Table S2), nucleoid volume fraction (circle values from Table S3), and proteins.
 395 Perturbations to primary fits provide bounds (dashed lines and grey shaded region). (B)
 396 Extrapolated volume fractions (bolded dashed lines) projecting beyond observed growth rates
 397 (solid lines) for ribosomes (purple curve, triangles), ternary complexes (red curve, circles), and
 398 proteins (blue curve, x's). Volume fractions are computed from cell parameter fits (**Methods**).
 399 Bounds for extrapolated volume fractions at hypothetical growth rates (light dashed lines and
 400 shading) are derived from permutations of the bounds for all cell parameters in panel A.
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Figure S12. Whether or not literature-determined values for ternary complex abundances account for peptidyl-tRNA does not impact voxel composition or trends. (A) Key growth-rate dependent trends in translation voxel composition resulting from the modeling used throughout our manuscript (solid line), in which we interpret ternary complex abundance measurements as not including peptidyl-tRNA, are equivalent to those resulting from assuming that ternary complex abundance measurements do include peptidyl-tRNA (dashed line). **(B)** The volume fraction of ribosomes (purple curve, triangles), ternary complexes (red curve, circles), and proteins (blue curve, x's), as well as total volume fraction (black curve, squares) are negligibly different for voxels constructed with the assumption that ternary complex measurements do not include peptidyl-tRNA (solid line) and the assumption that they do (dashed line).

415

416 **Figure S13. Faster elongation due to stoichiometric crowding is insensitive to changes in**
 417 **chemical kinetic parameters while sensitive to changes in transport physics. (A)** Accuracy of
 418 chemical kinetics: cartoon schematic illustrating how differences in salt concentrations between *in*
 419 *vitro* conditions in which chemical kinetic rates were measured and *in vivo* conditions being
 420 modeled could lead to different and perhaps faster kinetic rates than used in our simulations. **(B)**
 421 Impact of faster chemistry, instantaneous physics: our simulations with three-fold faster kinetic
 422 rates produce elongation latency (open circles) that closes the quantitative gap between our original
 423 elongation latency prediction using published *in vitro* kinetic rates (solid circles) and *in vivo*
 424 measurements of per-ribosome elongation time (solid black line). The essentiality of physics in
 425 this agreement is demonstrated by the lack of faster elongation in simulations with instantaneous
 426 transport (red triangles). Depiction of *E. coli* in (A) adapted with permission from Goodsell, 2009
 427 (27).
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Figure S14. (A-C) Our simulation overlap resolution step analysis shows that elongation latency, transport latency, and reaction latency each converge near our chosen overlap resolution step at the most crowded growth rate ($\mu = 3.0$ dbl/hr). Experimentally measured elongation latency at $\mu = 3.0$ dbl/hr is shown for reference in panel A (green line). **(D)** Overlaps resolved under threshold error converge to near 100% near our chosen number of overlap resolution steps. All simulations were for translation voxels at $\mu = 3.0$ dbl/hr. The dashed line corresponds to the overlap resolution steps used for simulations throughout the paper (three overlap resolution steps).

439 **Figure S15. Translation voxels avoid finite size effects.** The pair-correlation function $g(r)$
 440 between all possible combinations of pairing between ribosomes, ternary complexes (TC), and
 441 proteins (r is center-center separation) shows that all spatial correlations due to hard-sphere
 442 entropic exclusion decay at distances smaller than voxel sizes at all growth rates. Horizontal
 443 dashed line marks $g(r) = 1$. All simulations were performed using LAMMPS.

445
 446 **Figure S16. Size polydispersity of proteins in *E. coli*.** Dashed lines show the size of an average-
 447 sized protein, a ternary complex, and a ribosome.
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449
 450 **Figure S17. Plot of mass density (filled bars) and volume fraction (hashed bars) at three**
 451 **growth rates.** Data shown on a per-molecule and voxel basis. Data is tabulated and cited in our
 452 Supplementary Tables 1-4. Changes in volume fraction do not imply a one-to-one change in mass
 453 density.
 454

regardless of growth rate \rightarrow suppose 2 species have equal molecular mass: $m_1 = m_2$ but three-fold different per-molecule volume: $3 V_1 = V_2$ then the per-molecule mass-densities differ by three-fold: $\rho_1 = 3 \rho_2$

455
 456 **Figure S18. Mass density versus volume fraction.** (A) Mass density of a cell can remain constant
 457 across growth rate (left to right) but volume fraction can grow. (B) Mass density and volume
 458 fraction can both remain constant but only if stoichiometry is held fixed. In *E. coli*, the
 459 stoichiometry (relative abundance of translation molecules) is well known to vary with growth rate
 460 and thus represents case (a).

461 **Table S1. Estimation of elongating ribosome, ternary complex, and protein abundances at**
 462 **varying growth rates**
 463

Estimation of elongating ribosome abundance						
Doublings/hr	$\mu = 0.6$	$\mu = 1.0$	$\mu = 1.5$	$\mu = 2.0$	$\mu = 2.5$	$\mu = 3.0$
Ribosomes/cell ^a	8000	15000	26000	44000	61000	73000
Elongating Ribosomes/cell ^b	7000	13000 ^c	22000	37000	52000	62000
Estimation of ternary complex abundance						
Doublings/hr	$\mu = 0.4$	$\mu = 0.7$	$\mu = 1.07$	$\mu = 1.6$	$\mu = 2.5$	$\mu = 3.0$
tRNA:ribosome ratio ^d	12.5	9.5	7.5	7.5	7.0	7.0
Ribosomes/cell	5000 ^e	8000 ^f	15000 ^f	26000 ^f	61000	73000
tRNA/cell ^g	64000	76000	110000	190000	430000	510000
Charged tRNA/cell ^h	48000	57000	83000	143000	323000	383000
Ternary complex abundance ⁱ	48000	57000	83000	143000	323000	383000
Estimation of protein abundance						
Doublings/hr	$\mu = 0.6$	$\mu = 1.0$	$\mu = 1.5$	$\mu = 2.0$	$\mu = 2.5$	$\mu = 3.0$
$M_{\text{cytoplasm}}^j$	167	267	383	530	628	659
M_{mRNA}^j	0.5	0.9	1.5	2.6	3.6	4.3
M_{DNA}^j	7.6	9.5	12.0	14.7	17.2	19.4
N_{rib}^k	4000	14000	26000	38000	50000	62000
N_{tern}^k	57000	86000	138000	208000	295000	399000
N_{prot}^k	2.66×10^6	4.30×10^6	5.90×10^6	7.02×10^6	7.65×10^6	7.78×10^6

464
 465 ^aValues obtained from Dennis and Bremer, 2008.

466 ^bCalculated from ribosomes/cell using fraction of elongating ribosomes = 0.85 as reported in
 467 Dennis and Bremer, 2008.

468 ^cAs a secondary check, we used single cell mass spectrometry data from Schmidt et al., 2015 to
 469 calculate the abundance of ribosomes at $\mu = 0.83/\text{hr}$. We estimated ~17,000 ribosomes
 470 (RibosomeAbundanceEstimation.ipynb) by log averaging the reported abundances of fifty-four
 471 ribosomal proteins. Using the value of ~77% of ribosomes elongating at steady state as reported
 472 by Forchhammer and Lindahl, 1971, our estimated ~17,000 ribosomes corresponds to ~13,000
 473 elongating ribosomes, matching the value reported from Dennis and Bremer, 2008 at $\mu = 1.0$
 474 dbl/hr.

475 ^dValues obtained from Dong et al., 1996. The value at $\mu = 3.0$ dbl/hr was inferred via extrapolation
 476 of their reported data. In our modeling, we interpreted these measurements as representing only
 477 ternary complexes that are free or within the A-site; this interpretation does not impact our
 478 modeling results (**Figure S12**).

479 ^eWe estimated the number of ribosomes at $\mu = 0.4$ dbl/hr using the reported measurements of tRNA
480 and tRNA:ribosome ratios from Dong et al., 1996. Dong et al. performed six replicates of
481 measurements at 0.4 dbl/hr, and so six data points were included in our fitting shown in Figure S1.
482 ^fWe estimated the number of ribosomes at each given growth rate using the number of ribosomes
483 at the closest reported growth rate from the data of Dennis and Bremer, 2008.
484 ^gCalculated as the product of the tRNA:ribosome ratio and the number of ribosomes/cell
485 ^hApproximately 75%-80% of tRNA are typically charged with amino acids (31, 32). We assumed
486 uniform charging of 75% across all growth rates and types of tRNA.
487 ⁱWe assumed that all charged tRNA are found in ternary complexes (i.e., bound to GTP bound EF-
488 Tu) based on the excess abundance of EF-Tu in cells reported by Schmidt et al., 2015 and the fast
489 kinetic rates of EF-Tu binding to GTP and EF-Tu-GTP binding to charged tRNA reported by
490 Burnett et al., 2013, 2014.
491 ^jValues obtained from Dennis and Bremer, 2008. Units of fg/cell.
492 ^kDerived from the regression fit shown in Figure S1.

493 **Table S2. Estimation of cell volume at varying growth rates**
 494

Doublings/hr	$\mu =$ 0.25	$\mu =$ 0.42	$\mu =$ 0.56	$\mu =$ 0.58	$\mu =$ 0.68	$\mu =$ 0.71
Media ^a	Gal	Ac	GluN	Pyr	Fum	Suc
Volume (fL) ^b	1.9	2.4	2.9	2.1	2.4	2.3
Adjusted volume (fL) ^c	1.14	1.44	1.74	1.26	1.11	1.38

Doublings/hr	$\mu =$ 0.87	$\mu =$ 1.81	$\mu =$ 1.85	$\mu =$ 2.15	$\mu =$ 2.3
Media ^a	Glc	Gly+AA	Man+AA	Glc+AA	LB
Volume (fL) ^b	2.4	3.2	3.9	4.1	4.99
Adjusted volume (fL) ^c	1.44	2.15	2.34	2.46	2.4

502
 503 ^aGal = Galactose; Ac = Acetate; GluN = Glucosamine; Pyr = Pyruvate; Fum = Fumerate; Suc =
 504 Succinate; Glc = Glucose; Gly+AA = Glycerol + all amino acids; Man+AA = Mannose + all
 505 amino acids; Glc+AA = Glucose + all amino acids; LB = Lysogeny broth.

506 ^bValues obtained from Volkmer and Heinemann, 2011 using fluorescence microscopy.

507 ^cIn Radzikowski et al., 2016, a subset of measurements from Volkmer and Heinemann, 2011
 508 were redone at higher resolution using super-resolution imaging and found to be 30-50% smaller
 509 than estimated by Volkmer et al., 2011. We thus adjusted volume measurements by Volkmer and
 510 Heinemann, 2011, as discussed in Schmidt et al., 2015, to either the higher-fidelity
 511 measurements if the conditions were explicitly tested or reduced measurements by 40% if not.

512 **Table S3. Estimation of nucleoid volume fraction at varying growth rates**
 513

Doublings/hr	$\mu = 0.4$	$\mu = 1.36$	$\mu = 2.85$
Media	Alanine	Glucose	Tryptone
Nucleoid volume (fL) ^a	0.08	0.14	0.30
Cell volume (fL) ^a	0.46	1.06	2.72
Nucleoid volume fraction ^b	0.17	0.13	0.11

514

515 ^aValues obtained from Woldringh and Nanninga, 1985.

516 ^bCalculated by dividing the reported nucleoid volume by the reported cell volume.

517 **Table S4. Parameters not varying with growth rate**
 518

M_{rib}	2300 kDa
M_{tern}	69 kDa
M_{tRNA}	25 kDa
$M_{\text{amino acid}}$	110 Da
$M_{\text{EF-Tu}}$	43.2 kDa
M_{GTP}	523 Da
$M_{\text{prot}}^{\text{a}}$	28.5 kDa
$\bar{V}_{\text{prot}}^{\text{b}}$	$3.35 \times 10^{-8} \mu\text{m}^3$
$\rho_{\text{prot}}^{\text{c}}$	1.410 g/cm^3
$R_{\text{prot}}^{\text{d}}$	2.0 nm
$R_{\text{rib}}^{\text{de}}$	13 nm
$R_{\text{tern}}^{\text{df}}$	5.9 nm
k_B	$1.380649 \times 10^{-23} \text{ J/K}$
T	37 C
η	0.6913 mPa*s
D_{tern}	$56 \mu\text{m}^2/\text{s}$
D_{rib}	$25 \mu\text{m}^2/\text{s}$
D_{prot}	$165 \mu\text{m}^2/\text{s}$

519
 520 ^aWe computed the mass of individual average-sized proteins as described in the methods. Given
 521 an average amino acid mass of 108 Da, as reported by Bremer and Dennis, 2008, the protein mass
 522 corresponds to 264 amino acids on average. This protein length corresponds well to estimates in
 523 the literature of the average and median number of amino acids for a protein, 309 and 252 amino
 524 acids respectively (37), supporting our calculations.

525 ^bThe volume of an average-sized protein was calculated as described in the methods.

526 ^cValue obtained from Fischer et al., 2004.

527 ^dBiomolecule radius was calculated as described in the methods. Note that we use R and a
 528 interchangeably.

529 ^eMeasured using PDB 4V4Q from Schuwirth et al., 2005 as described in the methods.

530 ^fMeasured using PDB 1B23 from Nissen et al., 1999 as described in the methods.

531 **Table S5. tRNA-ribosome reaction kinetic parameters for non-cognate, near-cognate, and**
 532 **cognate tRNA**
 533

Kinetic Rates (s ⁻¹)	k_{1r}^{a*}	$k_{2f,cog,nr}^{b*}$	$k_{2r,cog}^{b*}$	$k_{2r,nr}^{b*}$	$k_{3,cog}^{b*}$	$k_{3,nr}^{b*}$	$k_{4,cog}^{c*}$	$k_{5,cog}^d$	$k_{6,cog}^e$
Data		1458	1.5	837	994	6.6			
		1535	2.7	837	2064	4.5			
		1535		837		2.4			
		2214		1305		0.8			
		837		1914		9.7			
		1535		994		13.8			
		1150							
Average Standard deviation	718	1475	2.1	1120	1529	6.3	209	200	32
	226	392	0.9	429	757	4.9	11	40	-

534

535 ^aMeasurements from Gromadski and Rodnina, 2004

536 ^bMeasurements from Gromadski et al., 2006

537 ^cMeasurements from Kothe and Rodnina, 2006

538 ^dMeasurements from Wohlgemuth et al., 2010

539 ^eBorg and Ehrenberg, 2015 made several measurements in varying buffer conditions. We chose
 540 their measurement that most corresponds to cell-like conditions (Polymix buffer with 1 mM free
 541 Mg²⁺ and 10μM EF-G).

542 *Kinetic rates were adjusted from 20 C to 37 C using the methods from Rudorf et al., 2014 and
 543 measurements of $k_{5,cog}$ at both 20 C and 37 C from Wohlgemuth et al., 2010.

544
545

Table S6. Frequency of tRNA and codon usage at varying growth rates

Frequency of tRNA^a					
Doublings/hr	$\mu = 0.4$	$\mu = 0.7$	$\mu = 1.07$	$\mu = 1.6$	$\mu = 2.5$
Ala1B	0.051	0.054	0.060	0.056	0.059
Ala2	0.009	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.010
Arg2	0.074	0.068	0.065	0.076	0.072
Arg3	0.010	0.012	0.007	0.008	0.006
Arg4	0.013	0.011	0.012	0.010	0.010
Arg5	0.006	0.007	0.007	0.008	0.006
Asn	0.019	0.018	0.018	0.019	0.020
Asp1	0.037	0.037	0.035	0.038	0.042
Cys	0.025	0.022	0.022	0.023	0.020
Gln1	0.012	0.012	0.016	0.010	0.012
Gln2	0.014	0.014	0.014	0.017	0.018
Glu2	0.073	0.072	0.070	0.078	0.082
Gly2	0.033	0.033	0.033	0.036	0.031
Gly3	0.068	0.071	0.072	0.064	0.070
His	0.010	0.010	0.012	0.010	0.012
Ile1	0.054	0.054	0.056	0.060	0.069
Leu1	0.069	0.069	0.072	0.069	0.061
Leu2	0.015	0.016	0.017	0.015	0.016
Leu3	0.010	0.011	0.012	0.010	0.009
Leu4	0.030	0.029	0.030	0.031	0.026
Leu5	0.018	0.016	0.017	0.011	0.010
Lys	0.030	0.031	0.031	0.028	0.029
Met fl	0.019	0.022	0.025	0.020	0.028
Phe	0.016	0.017	0.018	0.015	0.015
Pro1	0.014	0.011	0.014	0.009	0.007
Pro2	0.011	0.012	0.009	0.013	0.010
Pro3	0.009	0.009	0.009	0.008	0.007
Sec	0.003	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.003
Ser1	0.020	0.025	0.023	0.022	0.020
Ser2	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.004	0.004
Ser3	0.022	0.020	0.020	0.018	0.016
Ser5	0.012	0.012	0.012	0.011	0.012
Thr1	0.002	0.002	0.003	0.001	0.001
Thr2	0.009	0.009	0.009	0.009	0.009
Thr3	0.017	0.017	0.017	0.015	0.016
Thr4	0.014	0.014	0.014	0.015	0.019
Trp	0.015	0.013	0.014	0.013	0.015
Tyr1+Tyr2	0.031	0.029	0.027	0.032	0.026
Val1	0.060	0.055	0.047	0.061	0.057
Val2A+2B	0.020	0.020	0.022	0.020	0.019

Frequency of codon usage (1×10^{-3}) ^b					
Doublings/hr	$\mu = 0.4$	$\mu = 0.7$	$\mu = 1.07$	$\mu = 1.6$	$\mu = 2.5$
<i>GGG</i>	4.81	4.26	3.57	2.79	2.36
<i>GGA</i>	2.71	2.49	2.21	1.79	1.26
<i>GGU</i>	38.29	39.18	40.49	42.27	45.55
<i>GGC</i>	35.62	35.58	35.54	35.49	34.17
<i>GAG</i>	16.57	16.78	17.04	17.31	16.97
<i>GAA</i>	53.1	53.94	55.1	56.68	57.86
<i>GAU</i>	24.25	23.43	22.4	21.08	19.27
<i>GAC</i>	28.72	29.65	30.93	32.35	33.74
<i>GUG</i>	21.4	20.34	18.93	17.74	14.98
<i>GUA</i>	15.87	17.05	18.65	19.95	22.31
<i>GUU</i>	31.31	33.1	35.63	38.14	43.18
<i>GUC</i>	11.25	10.58	9.71	8.86	7.67
<i>GCG</i>	30.33	29.55	28.45	27.29	24.11
<i>GCA</i>	22.13	22.19	22.38	23.07	24.87
<i>GCU</i>	28.85	30.31	32.41	34.79	39.49
<i>GCC</i>	19.8	18.5	16.81	14.67	11.81
<i>AGG</i>	0.09	0.07	0.05	0.03	0.03
<i>AGA</i>	1.12	0.99	0.84	0.65	0.63
<i>AGU</i>	3.99	3.55	3.01	2.38	2.19
<i>AGC</i>	11.97	11.4	10.69	9.88	9.31
<i>AAG</i>	12.08	12.76	13.74	14.89	17.22
<i>AAA</i>	44.43	46.41	49.07	51.99	55.01
<i>AAU</i>	9.79	8.88	7.79	6.43	5.61
<i>AAC</i>	27.95	28.22	28.64	29.02	29.21
<i>AUG</i>	22.37	22.36	22.34	22.3	21.67
<i>AUA</i>	0.93	0.85	0.75	0.61	0.52
<i>AUU</i>	21.38	20.45	19.26	17.72	15.79
<i>AUC</i>	36.68	37.72	39.15	41.38	43.86
<i>ACG</i>	7.53	6.95	6.21	5.2	4.17
<i>ACA</i>	3.48	3.25	2.99	2.63	2.61
<i>ACU</i>	13.88	15.1	16.76	18.31	20.64
<i>ACC</i>	26.51	26.77	27.1	27.47	26.7
<i>UGG</i>	9.76	9.28	8.69	8.01	7.03
<i>UGA</i>	0.31	0.27	0.23	0.17	0.19
<i>UGU</i>	4.23	3.97	3.64	3.24	2.76
<i>UGC</i>	5.29	5.06	4.77	4.35	3.81
<i>UAU</i>	10.68	9.9	8.9	7.85	6.72
<i>UAC</i>	16.2	16.41	16.71	16.9	16.52
<i>UUG</i>	6.63	6.22	5.72	4.93	4.27
<i>UUA</i>	6.13	5.46	4.64	3.56	2.73
<i>UUU</i>	12.55	11.54	10.3	8.72	7.92
<i>UUC</i>	22.68	22.55	22.44	22.68	23.25

<i>UCG</i>	6.05	5.41	4.58	3.75	2.51
<i>UCA</i>	3.89	3.54	3.09	2.55	1.98
<i>UCU</i>	13.12	13.54	14.14	14.84	16.33
<i>UCC</i>	11.15	11.57	12.09	12.34	11.68
<i>CGG</i>	1.75	1.52	1.23	0.9	0.62
<i>CGA</i>	1.32	1.17	0.99	0.75	0.67
<i>CGU</i>	31.12	33.46	36.61	39.6	43.82
<i>CGC</i>	22.25	22.31	22.39	21.76	20.59
<i>CAG</i>	29.24	28.8	28.33	27.69	27.28
<i>CAA</i>	10.19	9.65	8.98	7.99	7.01
<i>CAU</i>	9.23	8.72	8.11	7.23	6.78
<i>CAC</i>	13.9	13.9	13.91	14.08	14.21
<i>CUG</i>	60.13	60.62	61.29	61.59	60.75
<i>CUA</i>	2.15	1.87	1.53	1.09	0.82
<i>CUU</i>	5.7	5.22	4.64	4.01	3.86
<i>CUC</i>	6.19	5.91	5.52	5.03	4.09
<i>CCG</i>	29.51	29.22	28.88	28.91	28.82
<i>CCA</i>	6.52	6.47	6.4	6.08	5.18
<i>CCU</i>	4.99	4.9	4.79	4.62	4.38
<i>CCC</i>	3.32	2.77	2.1	1.4	1.09

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547 ^aCalculated by renormalizing the molar ratio measurements reported in Dong et al., 1996 for each
548 growth rate

549 ^bMeasurements from Dong et al., 1996

550

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